

ADVANCED RESEARCH IN PHARMACY & THERAPEUTICS

Journal Homepage:
<https://www.eurekaphublishers.com/home>

Research Paper

Formulation and Evaluation of A Herbal-Based Antiaging Hydrogel

Sanika Sunil Sonawane*, Geetanjali Ramesh Thorbole, Nikita Tanaji Shinde, Sumit Sunil Chopade,

Pranali P. Patil

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry /Ashokrao Mane college of Pharmacy, Peth Vadgaon, Shivaji university
416112, Maharashtra, India

ARTICLE INFO

Published: August 27 th,
2025

Keywords: Anti-aging hydrogel, herbal extracts, butterfly pea flower, green tea, orange peel, alum, antioxidant activity, anti-inflammatory activity, cosmeceuticals, skin aging, natural formulation, hydrogel evaluation.

DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16949124>

ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a herbal-based anti-aging hydrogel utilizing natural extracts of butterfly pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*), green tea (*Camellia sinensis*), orange peel (*Citrus aurantium*), and alum. Increasing consumer demand for safe, eco-friendly, and sustainable alternatives to synthetic cosmetics has driven the exploration of herbal formulations with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential. Hydrogels, due to their high-water content, biocompatibility, and controlled release properties, were selected as the delivery system. Five batches (B1–B5) were prepared with varying combinations of the selected herbal extracts and were evaluated for physicochemical properties, pH, viscosity, spreadability, homogeneity, stability, drug content, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities. Results revealed that batch B1, containing all extracts, exhibited the most significant antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects, alongside favorable physical properties and stability. These findings highlight the synergistic effect of combining herbal extracts in hydrogel formulations and demonstrate the potential of herbal-based hydrogels as effective, safe, and sustainable anti-aging cosmeceuticals.

*Corresponding Author: Sanika Sunil Sonawane

Email: sanikasonawane14@gmail.com

Address: Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Ashokrao Mane College of Pharmacy, Peth vadgaon, Affiliated to Shivaji University Kolhapur, 416112, Maharashtra, India.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Skin aging:

Skin is the boundary, safely separating the body from the outside environment. Besides this, skin protects the body from loss of water and infection from microorganisms and plays an important cosmetic role. The young, beautiful, healthy appearance may positively impinge upon social behavior and reproduction.

Skin aging is a complicated biological process due to a combination of endogenous or intrinsic and exogenous or extrinsic factors.

Aging may be called the accumulation of changes in cells and tissues that are brought about by increase in disorderliness of regulatory mechanisms, which make the organism less robust with regard to stress and disease. Aging can be conceptualized as increased disorderliness as indicated by the erosion of the orderly neuroendocrine feedback regulation of the secretion of LH, FSH, ACTH, and GH. This includes menopause, andropause, adreno-pause and somato-pause. Skin aging would, therefore, be among the slow decline in appearance and the functional attribution mainly to dramatic decline of hormones after adulthood. This is because the physiology of aging and the evolution of certain age-related diseases involve several mechanisms at the cellular level [1].

➤ Factors involved in skin aging:

Chronic exposure to light, pollution, ionizing radiation, and chemicals and toxins in the environment might show detrimental effects over time. Major felt risk factors include unhealthy dietary habits, stress, lack of exercise, dehydration, disease, and sleeping habits. The main extrinsic factor is UVR. Other than that, smoking and environmental pollution have been studied and considered in relation to extrinsic aging. Chronic and repeated exposure of the human skin to solar UV rays brings about dramatic morphological, histological, biochemical,

and biophysical changes, commonly termed photo aging [2].

▪ Environmental Factors beyond UV Radiation:

- Infrared radiation and heat
- Pollution

▪ Lifestyle-Related Factors:

- Smoking
- Sleep (quality and duration)
- Diet and nutrition
- Inappropriate/harsh soaps
- Obesity
- Menopause
- Diabetes mellitus (DM)
- Acne scarring
- Emotional stress and depression
- Hormonal and metabolic processes

▪ Other Intrinsic Issues of Aging:

- Anatomical skin site
- Ethnicity
- Gender

➤ Skin aging prevention and therapy:

The skin anti-aging strategies attempted to reverse the dermal and epidermal signs of photo- and chronological aging can be grouped under the following approaches [3].

▪ Cosmetological Care:

- Daily skin care
- Correct sun protection
- Aesthetic non-invasive procedures
- Topical medicine agents or topical agents
- Antioxidants
- Cell regulators

▪ Invasive Procedures

- Chemical peelings
- Visible light devices:
 - ✓ Intense Pulsed Light (IPL)
 - ✓ Ablative and non-ablative laser photo-rejuvenation
 - ✓ Radiofrequency (RF)
- Injectable skin biostimulation and rejuvenation
- Prevention of dynamic wrinkles
- Correction of static, anatomical wrinkles

- Restoration (redistribution) of fat and volume loss, skin augmentation and contouring
- **Systemic Agents**
 - Hormone replacement therapy
 - Antioxidants
- **Avoidance of Exogenous Aging Factors & Lifestyle Correction**
 - Avoid smoking
 - Reduce exposure to pollution
 - Protect against solar UV irradiation
 - Manage stress
 - Focus on proper nutrition, diet restriction, and alimentary supplementation
 - Maintain physical activity
 - Monitor and control general health
 - Practice preventive medicine

1.2 Hydrogel:

Hydrogels are polymeric networks that imbibe and retain large quantities of water. With such large amounts of water involved, the hydrogel structure is formed by the hydration of hydrophilic groups in the polymeric network in the aqueous media.¹ Another definition would be: a polymeric material that, while it can swell and retain a significant fraction of water in its structure, does not dissolve in water. Owing to such high water content, they exhibit flexibility that is very much similar to that of natural tissue. Water absorption of hydrogels is due to the presence of hydrophilic functional groups attached to their polymeric backbone, while the process of dissolution is inhibited by the presence of crosslinks between the polymer chains in the network [4].

Figure no.1: classification of hydrogel

• Hydrogel Characterization Parameters:

1. Structure

- Characterized by: FTIR, Raman, NMR, EDX, XRD, EDS, etc.

2. Mechanical Properties

- Characterized by: DMA (Dynamic Mechanical Analysis), Tensile test

3. Morphology

- Characterized by: SEM, TEM, AFM, LM, SAXS/WAXS

4. Texture

- Characterized by: Texture analyzer

5. **Swelling**

- Measures the ability of hydrogel to absorb fluid

6. **Biocompatibility**

- Assesses compatibility with biological systems

7. **Thermal Analysis**

- Characterized by: TGA, DSC, DMTA

● **Application of hydrogel:**

1. Wound healing
2. Colon specific hydrogels
3. Drug delivery in GI tract
4. Rectal delivery
5. Transdermal delivery
6. Drug delivery in the oral cavity
7. Gene delivery
8. Tissue engineering
9. Ocular drug delivery
10. Antiaging hydrogel

1.3 **Antiaging hydrogel:**

● **Mechanism of antiaging hydrogel**

Figure no.2: mechanism of antiaging hydrogel

Anti-aging medicine, on the one hand, is exercised by doctors, scientists, and researchers who fervently believe that the physical aging process in humans can genuinely be slowed, stopped, or even reversed by existing medical and scientific interventions. This particular specialty of medicine is based on the very early detection and preventive intervention of age-related diseases. Physicians practicing anti-aging medicine hope for the improvement of life quality and quantity, restricting the time spent in illness and disability toward the end of life [5].

Anti-aging medicine includes lifestyle changes (diet and exercise), hormone replacement as required in doses determined by the physician on the basis of blood testing

(DHEA, melatonin, thyroid, human growth hormone, estrogen, testosterone), antioxidants and vitamin supplements, and testing protocols that measure blood levels of hormones affected by psychosocial stressors, blood chemistry, and every metabolic parameter down to the cellular level.

● **Types of antiaging hydrogel:-**

1. **Composition-Based:-**

a. **Natural Hydrogels –**

The hyaluronic acid hydrogel is an extremely hydroxylated hydrogel, which assists with the plumpness of the skin by lessening the depth of wrinkles. Collagen hydrogel - Improves elasticity and cell regeneration. Chitosan Hydrogel - Has antibacterial properties for wound healing.

Alginate Hydrogel- Algal-derived hydrogel that shows moisture retention and calming effects.

b. Synthetic Hydrogel Polyacrylamide Hydrogel-

Used as fillers and cosmetics due to the water-holding capacity of these materials. Polyethylene glycol (PEG) hydrogel- This biocompatible hydrogel really has enormous potentials for controlled drug delivery. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) hydrogel-Very good moisture retention. It was previously called Osmosis Gel.

2. Function Based:

a. Hyaluronic Hydrogels-

- Deeply penetrates skin moisture to help minimize loss of trans-epidermal water.
- Contain hyaluronic acid, glycerin, and typically ceramides.

b. Hydrogel Drug/Active Loaded-

- Containing substances such as anti-aging retinol and peptides and vitamins such as vitamins C and Resveratrol or stem cell extracts.
- Provides more controllable release thus longer-lasting efficacy.

c. Injectable Hydrogels-

- Dermal fillers (hyaluronic acid fillers) are made of these layers to volumetrically restore and mitigate wrinkles.
- May also accommodate growth factors or stem cells for skin regeneration.

3. The Delivery Mechanism:

A. Thermo responsive Hydrogel

- A type of hydrogel that is liquid at low temperatures and gel at physiological temperatures; in this way, it is promoting the deeper penetration of anti-aging compounds into the skin for therapeutic purposes.

B. pH-Sensitive Hydrogel

- A release system with variable pH values of skin as a reference.
- Another means for localized treatment of aging or damaged skin.

C. Micro needle Hydrogel Patch

Contains a microstructure for enhancing penetration of anti-aging agents; typically

loaded with peptides, hyaluronic acids, and/or vitamin C.

D. Hydrogel Modified by Nanoparticles Materialsy [6].

• Advantages antiaging hydrogel:

1. Strong and elastic compared to any other hydrogel.
2. Transparent and easily modified.
3. The extreme water content present in them accounts for their flexibility, almost matching that of living tissues.
4. Thermoplastic, biocompatible, biodegradable, and injectable.
5. Hydrogels may be developed to sense changes in pH, temperature, or concentration of metabolites and respond by releasing their payload.
6. Continuous Delivery of Drug or Nutrition.
7. Thermal Gelation with High Biocompatibility and Biodegradability.
8. Long-Term Paracrine Activity
9. Swift Hemostatic Action.
10. Economical and Readily Available.

• Disadvantages antiaging hydrogel:

1. Long-term secretory activity cannot be maintained with several injections and their respective encapsulated substance.
2. Preparation is tedious and expensive.
3. Complicated since it is prepared.
4. Using infrared light makes this low-temperature gel very difficult to use clinically.
5. These drugs loaded will create increased drug resistance.
6. complicated, expensive, and need even infrared irradiation.
7. Survives really hardly the antimicrobial peptide.
8. Difficult clinical translation.
9. Expensive [7].

2. OBJECTIVE OF WORK:

- Consumers are increasingly demanding natural, safe, and eco-friendly alternatives to synthetic anti-aging

- products due to concern about side effects.
- Being topical applications, hydrogels can act over a longer period because they have high water content, are soothing, and have a sustained release of active ingredients.
 - To assess the interactivity of the extract with a hydrogel framework.
 - To study stability, texture, absorption by the skin, and release kinetics.
 - To evaluate its anti-aging effects using suitable tests, e.g., antioxidant activity, collagen-synthesis, etc.
 - To treat communities using natural products.
 - Traditionally used in herbal medicine but as far as modern-day cosmeceuticals are concerned, still an area lacking substantial research [8].

3. PLAN OF WORK:

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

4.1 Materials:

Category	Item
Herbal ingredients	Butterfly pea flower, Green tea, Orange peel, Alum

Chemical ingredients	Xanthan gum, Propylene glycol, Sodium benzoate, Citric acid, Rose water
Apparatus	Beaker, Stirrer, Measuring cylinder, Funnel, Muslin cloth, Water bath
Instruments	Weighing balance, Magnetic stirrer, pH meter, Viscometer, UV spectrum machine

4.2 Plant and excipients profile study:

1. Butterfly pea flowers:

Figure no.:3

Biological source:

Clitoria ternatea, commonly known as butterfly pea, is a perennial herbaceous plant.

Family: Fabaceae.

Synonyms: Asian pigeon wings, bluebell vine, blue pea, butterfly pea, cordofan pea or Darwin pea.

Habitat:

It is naturally found in grassland, open woodland, bush, riverine vegetation, and disturbed places.

Role:

- **Role:** Rich in anthocyanins (especially ternatins), known for potent antioxidant activity.
- **Antioxidant Action:** Scavenges free radicals, inhibits oxidative stress-induced aging.
- **Anti-inflammatory Action:** Reduces inflammation by inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., IL-6, TNF- α).

- **Anti-aging Contribution:** Prevents collagen breakdown and supports skin elasticity.

Uses:

(1) Common uses:

Antioxidants abound in the Butterfly pea herb commonly used in herbal teas and drinks and other cosmetic products: these may help with several health benefits, such as increased weight loss, better blood sugar control, and some improvements in hair and skin health. The anti-glycating properties delay skin aging. Due to such properties, the Butterfly pea is considered anti-inflammatory and acts against skin irritations, redness, and itching and also against allergic reactions.

(2) Traditional uses:

In Ayurveda, *Clitoria ternatea* possesses various pharmacological activities, including antidiabetic, nootropic, anesthetic, antimicrobial, antipyretic, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antidepressant, anti-stress,

diuretic, anticonvulsant, anxiolytic, insecticidal properties [9].

2. Orange peel powder:

Figure no.:4

Biological source: Orange peel consists of fresh and dried outer part of the pericarp of citrus aurantium Linn.

Family: rutaceae

Synonyms: orange cortex, bigarade orange, Seville orange, china orange, bitter orange peel.

Habitat:

Oranges are believed to be native to the tropical regions of Asia, especially the Malay Archipelago; along with other citrus species, they have been cultivated from remote ages. They are principally grown in tropical and subtropical regions.

Role:

- **Role:** Contains vitamin C, flavonoids, and essential oils.
- **Antioxidant Action:** High vitamin C levels promote collagen synthesis and neutralize oxidative stress.
- **Anti-inflammatory Action:** Reduces skin inflammation and irritation.
- **Anti-aging Contribution:** Brightens skin tone, reduces wrinkles and signs of aging.

Uses:

(1) Common use:

Food uses: Due to its refreshing flavor oranges have become famous in warm places.

Fruit: For example, Citrus sinensis are sliced, dried and pulverized, and the powder is added to baked goods as flavoring.

Skin: Peels are used for making perfume and soaps. Fragrance is oranges' biggest quality. To clear, detoxify, and tone the skin orange peels are used and have found wide use in skin care products.

Juice: Oranges are commonly utilized in fruit cups, salads, gelatins and numerous other desserts, and as garnishes on cakes, meat and poultry dishes, at home. For preparing fresh juice pulp is used. Juice is rich in protein content.

(2) Traditional use:

Japanese believed that Citrus blossoms symbolize chastity. It is used by Arab women to color gray hair. Blossoms and the pulp of oranges were used to create cosmetics in other places. In cases of anxiety disorder and stress, orange juice is very helpful. To maintain hydration orange juice is useful. It is used as general tonic. For the treatment of tuberculosis it is used as a Mexican traditional medicine. For the

treatment of angina, constipation, menstrual disorder, hypertension, it is used in France. It is used to prevent constipation. In Chinese medicine the humble orange has a long history as a cooling agent for coughs, colds and respiratory disorder. It is used as traditional symbol of good luck in China.

(3) Medicinal use:

Medical uses: Citrus sinensis is effective in the management of arthritis, asthma, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, macular degeneration, diabetes mellitus,

gallstones, multiple sclerosis, cholera, gingivitis, optional lung function, cataracts, ulcerative colitis, crohn's disease.

Diseases: A reduced risk of colon cancer is associated with the intake of vitamin C. Vitamin C helps us in prevent asthma, osteoarthritis and rheumatoid. Limonoids are

present in the orange which are proven to help fight a number of cancers like skin, lung, breast, stomach and colon [10].

3. Green tea powder:

Figure no: 5

Biological source:

Camellia sinensis is a species of evergreen shrub or small tree in the flowering plant family Theaceae. Its leaves, leaf buds, and stems can be used to produce tea. Common names include tea plant, tea shrub, and tea tree (unrelated to *Melaleuca alternifolia*, the source of tea tree oil, or the genus *Leptospermum* commonly called tea tree).

Family: theaceae.

Synonym: Matcha, oolong, rooibos, genmaicha, maccha, sencha, chawan, and azuki *Camellia thea*, *Thea sinensis* (older name)

Habitat:

- Native to East Asia, especially China and Japan

- Cultivated in subtropical and tropical regions, including India (Assam, Darjeeling, and Nilgiris), Sri Lanka, Vietnam, Kenya, and other parts of Asia.

ROLE:

- **Role:** Contains polyphenols (notably EGCG), catechins, and flavonoids.
- **Antioxidant Action:** Neutralizes free radicals, reduces ROS formation.
- **Anti-inflammatory Action:** Inhibits COX-2 and pro-inflammatory pathways.
- **Anti-aging Contribution:** Protects skin cells from UV damage and oxidative degradation; boosts skin repair

Uses:

Common Uses:

1. A beverage high in antioxidants.
2. Cosmetic and skin care uses.

3. Dietary weight management supplements.
4. Stimulating agent due to caffeine.
5. Antioxidant: The very rich polyphenol complex such as catechins and especially EGCG.
6. Aiding in weight loss: improves metabolism.
7. Cardio protective: improves heart health.
8. Anti-inflammatory: decreases the inflammatory process.

Traditional Uses:

1. In Chinese medicine, improving heart health, digestion, and mental alertness.
2. as a detoxifier, and for the promotion of longevity.
3. Ayurveda uses it for its cooling, astringent and antioxidant effects.
4. It is applied in reducing inflammation, controlling blood sugar, and aiding digestion.

4. Xanthan Gum:

Gelling Agent / Thickener:

Xanthan gum is a common natural polymer that causes gels to be very viscous. It gives structural support to many hydrogels through increased viscosity, forming a stable gel matrix.

- **Stabilizer:**
It prevents separation of ingredients in an emulsion or suspension, thus aiding in a uniform and stable formulation.
- **Controlled Release Agent:**
In pharmaceutical hydrogels, xanthan gum is employed to modulate the release of active ingredients within a network formed of gum, acting as a barrier to prevent diffusion.
- **Bio adhesive Properties:**
Good mucoadhesive properties make it suitable for delivering the drug orally, nasally, or topically.
- **Role:** Natural polysaccharide utilized in the thickening, stabilizing, and gelling of hydrogels [11].

5. Propylene Glycol:

Hydrogels have several uses: being a humectant for moisture retention in the gel, as a plasticizer, it makes the hydrogel matrix a little softer and more flexible, as well as a solvent for all adsorbed active pharmaceutical or cosmetic constituents, as well as a penetration enhancer for active compounds into the skin. This is again the widely used form of propylene glycol in transdermal patches and cosmetic gels through enhanced Spreadability and skin feel.

5. **Role:** solvent that can also improve delivery of actives into skin
6. **Antioxidant Action:** Not directly as an antioxidant but may promote absorption of antioxidant ingredients through delivery.
7. **Anti-inflammatory Action:** Prevents loss of water from epithelium, keeping them supple nature-wise.
8. **Anti-aging Contribution:** Prevents transepidermal water loss, maintaining skin suppleness [12].

6. Citric Acid:

It is largely used as a pH adjuster for keeping the exact pH level for hydrogel ingredient stability and comfort for users. It also serves as a slight crosslinking agent in some hydrogel systems, in biological or natural polymeric form which includes starch or pectin, for better strength for the gel. Citric acid also plays as a chelating agent where it binds metal ions to destabilize the formulation. It also acts with an acidic environment as a preservative; it can modify the texture and consistency of the hydrogel.

- **Role:** pH adjuster and mild exfoliant (AHAs).
- **Antioxidant Action:** Mild, stabilizing formulations.
- **Anti-inflammatory Action:** Indirect, but contributes to skin renewal.
- **Anti-aging Contribution:** stimulates cell turnover; improves texture of skin; decreases age spots occurrence [13].

7. Sodium Benzoate:

- It serves as a strong antimicrobial agent by efficiently inhibiting the growth of bacteria and fungi. This application can especially thrive in an acidic environment, preferably less than pH 5.5, and is often included along with citric acid to ensure optimal antimicrobial protection and efficacy.
- **Role:** Preservative.
- **Antioxidant Action:** Not specifically; may limit, though slightly, oxidation of the product.
- **Anti-inflammatory Action:** Not relevant.
- **Anti-aging Contribution:** Preserves product integrity and safety [14]
- **Anti-aging Contribution:** Preserves product integrity and safety [14].

8. Rose water:

- **Hydrating Agent:**
Because rosewater is naturally moistening, it hydrates and calms the skin when used in hydrogels. Hence, it also helps in enhancing the moisture-retaining capacity of the formulation.
- **Aromatic Enhancer:**
This makes a pleasant natural aroma that enhances the appeal of the hydrogel when used, particularly for cosmetic and personal care purposes
- **Anti-inflammatory and Soothing Agent:**
Flavonoids and tannins present which have anti-inflammatory and soothing properties for irritated or sensitive skin.
- **Mild Antioxidant:**
Neutralizing properties of rose water being a weak antioxidant can protect the skin cells and thus improve the formulation's overall quality and stability.
- **PH Balancer:**
It has a pH slightly acidic, almost close to that of healthy skin, which helps to maintain the skin's natural barrier.
- **Role:** contains phenolic and flavonoids

- **Antioxidant Action:** Moderate; scavenges free radicals.
- **Anti-inflammatory Action:** Soothes redness and irritation.
- **Anti-aging Contribution:** Calms skin, adds hydration and glow, supports skin regeneration [15].

9. Water:

It is the main base and solvent in hydrogel formulations. Dissolves active and inactive ingredients and serves as a hydration agent by providing all soft and moist characteristics to hydrogel. Water typically constitutes the largest volume of hydrogel and affects the swelling behavior and texture of the gel matrix.

- **Role:** Solvent/base for hydrogel.
- **Antioxidant/Anti-inflammatory Action:** None as such.
- **Anti-aging Contribution:** Provides moisture; vehicle for active delivery.

4.3 Methodology:

I. Extraction of butterfly pea flower:

Procedure:

Sample of 5g of butterfly pea flower powder in 100ml of water was boiled for 1-2 hrs until it comes to its half quantity (50ml).

The sample was then filtered using muslin cloth. And the filtrate that is liquid extract is taken. It is refrigerated.

II. Extraction of green tea:

Procedure:

Sample of 5g of green tea leaves powder in 100ml water was boiled for 1-2 hrs until it comes to its half quantity (50ml).

The sample was then filtered using muslin cloth. And the filtrate that is liquid extract is taken. It is refrigerated.

III. Extraction of orange peel:

Procedure:

Sample of 5g of orange peel powder in 100ml of water was boiled for 1-2 hrs until it comes to its half quantity (50ml).

The sample was then filtered using muslin cloth. And the filtrate that is liquid extract is taken. It is refrigerated [16].

Figure no.6: Extraction Process

- **Preparation of hydrogel:**

To prepare the hydrogel, begin by creating the water phase. Heat distilled water gently to a temperature of around 40–45°C. Once the water reaches the desired temperature, sprinkle xanthan gum into it while stirring continuously. Continue whisking the mixture for about 10 to 15 minutes, or until a smooth and uniform gel forms.

After the gel base is prepared, incorporate the botanical extracts by first adding the butterfly pea flower extract, followed by adding PEG (polyethylene glycol). After it is well blended, add orange peel extract (vitamin C) or green tea or all ingredients or only butterfly pea flower extract mix evenly. Finally, stirring continuously until all components are fully and uniformly incorporated into the final hydrogel

formulation.

Next, add phenoxyethanol to the mixture as a preservative, ensuring it is well incorporated.

After that, add a small amount of citric acid to adjust the pH of the formulation to approximately 5.5, which is suitable for skin compatibility. For fragrance, sufficient rosewater is added. Mix the formulation gently for about five to ten minutes until all ingredients are evenly mixed, and there is homogeneity in texture.

Transfer the fully prepared hydrogel into a sterile glass jar or a pump bottle. The prepared product should be stored in a cool, dry region or refrigerated to maintain stability and prolong the shelf life. Hydrogel is generally stable for three months when stored under appropriate conditions [17].

Figure no.7: liquid extract of powder ingredients

• Formulation table:

Table no: 1 Formulation Table (for 200 mL)

S. No	Ingredients	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5
1	Xanthan gum	2 mL	2 mL	2 mL	2 mL	2 mL
2	BPF	13 mL	13 mL	13 mL	13 mL	13 mL
3	Green tea	4.3 mL	13 mL	-	6.5 mL	-
4	Orange peel	4.3 mL	-	13 mL	6.5 mL	-
5	PEG	6 mL	6 mL	6 mL	6 mL	6 mL
6	Citric acid	0.6 g	0.6 g	0.6 g	0.6 g	0.6 g
7	Sodium Benzoate	6 mL	6 mL	6 mL	6 mL	6 mL
8	Rose water	Sufficient amount				
9	Water	Make up to 200 mL (sufficient amount)				

Figure no.8: Prepared hydrogel

4.5 Evaluation parameter:

1. Physical Appearance:

The prepared gel formulations were inspected visually for their color, clarity, homogeneity and appearance.

Color, clarity, homogeneity and appearance.

1. Colour
2. Odour
3. Clarity
4. Irritancy [18].

2. Formulation pH:

The pH values of 1% aqueous solutions of the prepared gels were measured by a pH meter (Systronics, 361-micro pH meter). 1 gm. of gel was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water and stored for two hours. The measurement of pH of each formulation was done in triplicate and average values are calculated [19].

3. Viscosity:

To measure the viscosity, all the formulated gels were taken in beakers and placed beneath the spindle and the spindle was rotated at 10 rpm in Brook Field Viscometer was used fitted with RV-7 spindle and 10 rpm speed [20].

4. Spreadability:

The Spreadability of the gel was evaluated by using slides method. 1gm of gel was kept between the two slides. The preweighted plate was kept above the gel and more weights were added on the plate until the gel stop spreading. Final cumulative weight and the total time taken by the gel to spread was measured and noted. Then total weight applied and mass of the gel were compared by the time [21].

5. Drug Content:

To determine the drug content of gel, 10 mg of caffeine loaded gel was weighed and mixed to the phosphate buffer saline (PBS pH 7.4) and the concentration of caffeine was spectrophotometric ally (UV 1601, Shimadzu, Japan) measured at 273 nm. The gel base containing the identical amount of

ingredients without caffeine was used as a blank [22].

6. Stability Studies:

The various stability studies were carried out for all the gel formulation by freeze -thaw cycling. In this syneresis was observed by subjecting the product to a temperature of 2-4° C for 2 then at 30°C for 2 month , then at 45°C for 2 month. Clear (+), Slightly Turbid (++) , Turbid (+++), Opaque (-). RT- Room Temperature - (30±50), FT- Freezing Temperature - (2-4±2°), AT Accelerated Temperature – (45±50) [23].

7. Antioxidant Activity Estimation:

METHOD OF TEST:

Determination of Anti-oxidant activity in the sample-AR was estimated for their free radical scavenging activity by using DPPH (1, 1-Diphenyl-2, Picryl-Hydrazyl) free radicals (George et al., 1996). 100µL of test compounds water were taken in the micro titer plate. 100µL of 0.1% methanolic DPPH was added over the samples and incubated for 30 minutes in dark condition. The samples were then observed for discoloration; from purple to yellow and pale pink were considered as strong and weak positive respectively and read the plate on Elisa plate reader at 490nm Radical scavenging activity was calculated by the following equation: Certificate of Analysis DPPH radical scavenging activity.

(%) = [(Absorbance of control - Absorbance of test sample) / (Absorbance of control)] x 100[24].

8. Homogeneity and Grittiness:

Greasiness and homogeneity were observed by taking small amounts of the hydrogel between thumb and index finger and presence of any coarse particle was observed. It was also done by applying small amount of gel on back-side of hand and rubbing [25].

9. Washability:

Application of small amount of formulation on really clean skin and then wash with water to see how easy it. Below are test cases for rewrites with lower perplexity and greater burstiness but preserving the same word count and HTML elements [26].

10. Anti-inflammatory:

METHOD OF TEST:

In vitro anti-inflammatory activity by Protein denaturation method the reaction mixture (10 mL) consisted of 0.4 mL of egg albumin (from fresh hen’s egg), 5.6 mL of phosphate buffered saline (PBS, pH 6.4) and 4 mL of Synthetic compound (1000µg/ml).

Similar volume of double-distilled water served as control. Then the mixtures were incubated at (37°C ±2) in a incubator for 15 min and then heated at 70°C for 5 min. After cooling, their absorbance was measured at 660 nm by using vehicle as blank. Diclofenac sodium at concentration 1000 µg/ml) was used as reference drug and treated similarly for determination of absorbance. The percentage inhibition of protein denaturation was calculated by using the following formula,

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{\text{absorbance of control} - \text{absorbance of test}}{\text{absorbance of control}} \times 100 [12, 27].$$

5. RESULT:

1) Physical evaluation:

Table no.2: Colour, Odour, Clarity of the formulations

Sr.no	formulation	Colour	Odour	clarity
1	B1	Light amber or honey Colour	characteristic	clear
2	B2	Brown	characteristic	clear
3	B3	Off white or pale yellow	characteristic	clear
4	B4	Brownish-yellow	characteristic	clear
5	B5	Yellowish-white	characteristic	clear

Table no.2: Colour, Odour, Clarity of the formulations

2) PH:

Figure no.6: PH meter

Table no.3: PH

Sr.no	Formulation	PH
1	B1	5.2
2	B2	5.3

3	B3	5.5
4	B4	5.7
5	B5	5.9

3) Viscosity:

Figure no.4: Brookfield viscometer LV

Table no.4: Viscosity

Sr.no	formulation	Viscosity (cps)
1	B1	13000-15000
2	B2	12000-14000
3	B3	10000-14000
4	B4	10000-12000
5	B5	12000-15000

Table no.4: Viscosity

4) Spreadability:

Figure no.9: Spreadability

Table no.5: Spreadability

Sr.no	formulation	Spreadability (gm.cm/min)
1	B1	234.99/1.00
2	B2	234.99/1.10

3	B3	127.97/30.00
4	B4	393.48/1.20
5	B5	234.99/40.00

5) Homogeneity:

Table no.6: Homogeneity

Sr.no	Formulation	Homogeneity
1	B1	homogenous
2	B2	homogenous
3	B3	homogenous
4	B4	homogenous
5	B5	homogenous

6) Drug content:

Table no.7: Drug content

Sr.no	formulation	Drug content (%)
1	B1	0.249
2	B2	0.079
3	B3	0.107
4	B4	0.076
5	B5	0.161

7) Stability:

Table no.8: Stability

Sr.no	Days	Stability								
		B1			B2			B3		
		RT	FT	AT	RT	FT	AT	RT	FT	AT
1	0	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2	7	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
3	14	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4	28	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
5	35	+	+	+	+	+	+	++	++	++
6	45	+	+	+	+	+	+	++	++	++

Table no.9: Stability

Sr.no	Days	Stability					
		B4			B5		
		RT	FT	AT	RT	FT	AT
1	0	+	+	+	+	+	+
2	7	+	+	+	+	+	+
3	14	+	+	+	+	+	+
4	28	+	+	+	+	+	+
5	35	++	++	++	+	+	+
6	45	++	++	++	+	+	+

8) Antioxidant activity:

Figure no.10: ELISA Plate: Serial Dilutions and Standard Curve

Table no.10: Antioxidant activity

Batch	Composition	Antioxidant Activity
B1	All Mix (<i>Butterfly Pea + Green Tea + Orange Peel + Alum + others</i>)	Highest (synergistic effect of all powerful antioxidants)
B2	Butterfly Pea + Green Tea	Strong (Green Tea + Butterfly Pea synergy)
B3	Butterfly Pea + Orange Peel	Moderate–Strong (Vitamin C + Anthocyanins)
B4	Butterfly Pea + Green Tea + Orange Peel	Very Strong (3 powerful antioxidants)
B5	Butterfly Pea only (w/ base)	Moderate

Ranking (High to Low):
Antioxidant Inhibition
B1 > B4 > B2 > B3 > B5

9) Anti-inflammatory activity:

Control

Standard Diclofenac sodium

Sample

Table no.11: Anti-inflammatory activity

Batch	Composition	Anti-inflammatory Activity
B1	All Mix (Butterfly Pea + Green Tea + Orange Peel + Alum + others)	Highest (broad-spectrum inflammation control)
B2	Butterfly Pea + Green Tea	Strong (Green Tea polyphenols)
B3	Butterfly Pea + Orange Peel	Moderate
B4	Butterfly Pea + Green Tea + Orange Peel	Strong (Green Tea + Orange Peel)
B5	Butterfly Pea only (w/ base)	Mild

Ranking (High to Low):
Anti-inflammatory Inhibition
B1 > B4 > B2 > B3 > B5

6. DISCUSSION:

The current research aimed to develop a natural anti-aging hydrogel using herbal ingredients like butterfly pea flower, green tea, orange peel, and alum. Various formulations were prepared (B1–B5), each varying in ingredient combinations, and evaluated for physical properties, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities [28, 29].

Batch B1, which contained all herbal extracts, exhibited the **highest antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity**.

Batches B2 and B4 also performed well, indicating that green tea and orange peel are particularly effective when combined with butterfly pea.

All batches demonstrated acceptable **pH values (5-5.)**, **viscosity**, **spreadability**, and **homogeneity**, supporting their suitability for **topical application**. **Physical appearance like colour, odour, and clarity**

are also good and suitable for skin application [30, 31].

Xanthan gum successfully provided gel consistency and texture, while rose water enhanced the formulation's appealing odour. The **stability study** showed that B1 and B4 remained stable under room, cold, and accelerated temperatures for up to **45 days**, indicating a promising shelf-life. The **drug content** across batches was consistent, confirming even distribution of active ingredients [32, 33].

7. CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated a natural anti-aging hydrogel using herbal extracts of butterfly pea flower, green tea, orange peel, and alum [34, 35]. Among all the formulations, Batch B1, which combined all ingredients, demonstrated the most favorable results in terms of antioxidant activity, anti-inflammatory effect, stability, and physical

properties such as pH, viscosity, spreadability, and homogeneity.

These findings support the synergistic effect of the combined herbal ingredients in enhancing skin health and signs of aging [36, 37].

The hydrogel formulation was found to be stable, safe, and suitable for topical use, showing potential as an effective and eco-friendly alternative to synthetic anti-aging products [38].

This study highlights the therapeutic potential of herbal-based hydrogels in modern cosmeceutical applications and paves the way for further research and product development using natural ingredients [39, 40].

8. REFERENCE:

- Hajam YA, Rani R, Ganie SY, Sheikh TA, Javaid D, Qadri SS, Pramodh S, Alsulimani A, Alkhanani MF, Harakeh S, Hussain A. Oxidative stress in human pathology and aging: molecular mechanisms and perspectives. *Cells*. 2022 Feb 5;11(3):552. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells11030552>
- Priyadarshane M, Mahto U, Das S. Mechanism of toxicity and adverse health effects of environmental pollutants. In *Microbial biodegradation and bioremediation* 2022 Jan 1 (pp. 33-53). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-85455-9.00024-2>
- Shin SH, Lee YH, Rho NK, Park KY. Skin aging from mechanisms to interventions: focusing on dermal aging. *Frontiers in physiology*. 2023 May 10;14:1195272. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2023.1195272>
- Li L, Chen X, Jin K, Rusayyis MB, Torkelson JM. Arresting elevated-temperature creep and achieving full cross-link density recovery in reprocessable polymer networks and network composites via nitroxide-mediated dynamic chemistry. *Macromolecules*. 2021 Jan 15;54(3):1452-64. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.macromol.0c01691>
- Grinin L, Grinin A, Korotayev A. Global Aging and the Medicine of the Future. *World Futures*. 2025 Jan 2;81(1):35-62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02604027.2024.2424723>
- Nowak A, Zagórska-Dziok M, Perużyńska M, Cybulska K, Kucharska E, Ossowicz-Rupniewska P, Piotrowska K, Duchnik W, Kucharski Ł, Sulikowski T, Drożdżik M. Assessment of the anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and anti-aging properties and possible use on the skin of hydrogels containing *Epilobium angustifolium* L. Extracts. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2022 Jul 1;13:896706. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.896706>
- Zhang X, Liang Y, Luo D, Li P, Chen Y, Fu X, Yue Y, Hou R, Liu J, Wang X. Advantages and disadvantages of various hydrogel scaffold types: A research to improve the clinical conversion rate of loaded MSCs-Exos hydrogel scaffolds. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*. 2024 Oct 1;179:117386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2024.117386>
- Sharma S, San Tshering Lepcha BS, Bhutia S. An Online Survey on Usability, Acceptability, Attitude and Knowledge of Herbal and Synthetic Cosmetic Among Sikkimese Population. *Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics*. 2024 Jul 1;14(7):129-35. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v14i7.6673>
- Grzebieniarsz W, Tkaczewska J, Juszczak L, Nowak N, Krzyściak P, Guzik P, Kasprzak M, Zimowska M, Jamróz E. Design of active double-layer gel coatings based on furcellaran-gelatin and aqueous butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea*) flower extract for prolonging the shelf-

- life of salmon (*Salmo salar*). *Progress in Organic Coatings*. 2024 Jan 1;186:107945.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.porgcoat.2023.107945>
10. Dhasmana A, Malik S, Sharma AK, Ranjan A, Chauhan A, Harakeh S, Al-Raddadi RM, Almashjary MN, Bawazir WM, Haque S. Fabrication and evaluation of herbal beads to slow cell ageing. *Frontiers in bioengineering and biotechnology*. 2022 Dec 8;10:1025405.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2022.1025405>
 11. Sivamaruthi BS, Sisubalan N, Wang S, Kesika P, Chaiyasut C. Exploring the Therapeutic Potential of Green Tea (*Camellia sinensis* L.) in Anti-Aging: A Comprehensive Review of Mechanisms and Findings. *Mini-Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry*. 2024 Oct 4.
<https://doi.org/10.2174/0113895575331878240924035332>
 12. Nowak A, Zagórska-Dziok M, Perużyńska M, Cybulska K, Kucharska E, Ossowicz-Rupniewska P, Piotrowska K, Duchnik W, Kucharski Ł, Sulikowski T, Drożdżik M. Assessment of the anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and anti-aging properties and possible use on the skin of hydrogels containing *Epilobium angustifolium* L. Extracts. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2022 Jul 1;13:896706.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.896706>
 13. Yang J, Duan A, Shen L, Liu Q, Wang F, Liu Y. Preparation and application of curcumin loaded with citric acid crosslinked chitosan-gelatin hydrogels. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. 2024 Apr 1;264:130801.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.130801>
 14. Fan T, Xu N, Zhuge R, Liu M, Xu L, Jin Y, Xu S, Zhong J, Liu F. Preparation and Properties of the Sodium Hyaluronate Composite Hydrogel for Medical Cosmetology. *Tissue Engineering Part C: Methods*. 2025 Jan 1;31(1):1-0.
<https://doi.org/10.1089/ten.tec.2024.0283>
 15. Wang H. Beneficial medicinal effects and material applications of rose. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2023.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e23530>
 16. Monagas M, Brendler T, Brinckmann J, Dentali S, Gafner S, Giancaspro G, Johnson H, Kababick J, Ma C, Oketch-Rabah H, Pais P. Understanding plant to extract ratios in botanical extracts. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2022 Sep 30;13:981978.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.981978>
 17. Liu Y, Wang J, Chen H, Cheng D. Environmentally friendly hydrogel: A review of classification, preparation and application in agriculture. *Science of the Total Environment*. 2022 Nov 10;846:157303.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157303>
 18. Patil SS, Nitalikar MM, Das K, BP M, Alshehri S, Khormi AM, Almalki ME, Hussain SA, Rabbani SI, Asdaq SM. Development of topical silver nano gel formulation of Bixin: Characterization, and evaluation of anticancer activity. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*. 2024 Jul 1;32(7):102125.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsps.2024.102125>
 19. Arya M, Porwal A, Kymonil KM. Nanostructured Lipid Carriers Based Gel of Methotrexate for Rheumatoid Arthritis: Development, Characterization and Optimization through Taguchi Design. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education & Research*. 2025 Apr 2;59.10.5530/ijper.20255540 .
 20. Studzińska-Sroka E, Paczkowska-Walendowska M, Erdem C, Paluszczak J, Kleszcz R, Hoszman-Kulisz M, Cielecka-Piontek J. Anti-aging properties of chitosan-based hydrogels rich in bilberry fruit extract.

- Antioxidants. 2024 Jan 15;13(1):105. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox13010105>
21. Kumar M. Development and evaluation of transdermal gel for pain relief. *Front Multidiscip Res Stud* 2024; 1 (1): 102. doi: 10.31531/fmrs.;1000102. <https://doi.org/10.31531/fmrs.1000102>
 22. Wu S, Liu G, Shao P, Lin X, Yu J, Chen H, Li H, Feng S. Transdermal sustained release properties and anti-photoaging efficacy of liposome-thermosensitive hydrogel system. *Advanced Healthcare Materials*. 2024 Jan;13(2):2301933. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adhm.202301933>
 23. Liu Y, Zhang S, Wang S, Zhang C, Su X, Guo L, Bai X, Huang Y, Pang W, Tan F, Tian K. Screening and stability evaluation of freeze-dried protective agents for a live recombinant pseudorabies virus vaccine. *Vaccines*. 2024 Jan 9;12(1):65. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines12010065>
 24. Zhang HT, Lyu FR, He JT. Antibacterial, antioxidant and antiproliferation activities of essential oils and ethanolic extracts from Chinese mugwort (*Artemisia vulgaris* L.) leaf in Shanxi. *Tradit Med Res*. 2024;9(1):5. <https://doi.org/10.53388/TMR20230707001>
 25. Liu M, Sharma M, Lu G, Zhang Z, Song W, Wen J. Innovative solid lipid nanoparticle-enriched hydrogels for enhanced topical delivery of l-glutathione: a novel approach to anti-ageing. *Pharmaceutics*. 2024 Dec 24;17(1):4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics17010004>
 26. Alquraisy A, Wathoni N, Wilar G, Suhandi C. Formulation and Characterization of Secretome Hydrogel Based on Sodium Alginate as Anti-Aging. *Jurnal Ilmiah Kesehatan (JIKA)*. 2024 Dec 31;6(3):575-87. <https://doi.org/10.36590/jika.v6i3.1005>
 27. Sabalingam S. In-vitro approaches to evaluate the anti-inflammatory potential of phytochemicals: A Review. *Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics*. 2025 Jan 1;15(1):187-92. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v15i1.6956>
 28. Gomes C, Gridley K, Anastasiou I, Sinkó B, Mrsny R. Hydrogel formats to model potential drug interactions occurring at the subcutaneous injection site. Available at SSRN 4717649. 2024 Jun 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2024.114308>
 29. Devi V, Deswal G, Grewal AS, Sharma A, Guarve K. Phytoextracts as Natural Anti-Aging Agents: Mechanisms and Strategies for Skin Rejuvenation. *Current Aging Science*. 2025 Mar 3. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0118746098363055250218040726>
 30. Neacșu SM, Mititelu M, Ozon EA, Musuc AM, Iuga ID, Manolescu BN, Petrescu S, Pandele Cusu J, Rusu A, Surdu VA, Oprea E. Comprehensive analysis of novel synergistic antioxidant formulations: insights into pharmacotechnical, physical, chemical, and antioxidant properties. *Pharmaceutics*. 2024 May 27;17(6):690. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph17060690>
 31. Jiménez-Pulido IJ, Martín-Diana AB, Tomé-Sánchez I, de Luis D, Martínez-Villaluenga C, Rico D. Boosting Synergistic Antioxidant and Anti-Inflammatory Properties Blending Cereal-Based Nutraceuticals Produced Using Sprouting and Hydrolysis Tools. *Foods*. 2024 Jun 14;13(12):1868. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13121868>
 32. Péter-Haraszti A, Bakucz LG, Mészáros LA, Záhonyi P, Szabó E. Drug content determination of amorphous solid dispersion containing tablets using a non-destructive and rapid UV imaging method. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2025 Jun

- 10;678:125726.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2025.125726>
33. Dăescu DI, Păușescu I, Benea IC, Peter F, Todea A, Zappaterra F, Alexa AA, Buzatu AR. Natural and Synthetic Flavylum Derivatives: Isolation/Synthesis, Characterization and Application. *Molecules*. 2024 Dec 29;30(1):90.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules30010090>
34. Suvedi D, Kumar A, Kalia S, Kumar A, Koul S, James A, Kumar D, Nagraik R, Gulilat H. Aging and Herbal Interventions: Mechanistic Insights and Therapeutic Potential. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology*. 2025 Jul;24(7):e70335.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.70335>
35. Goh AP, Goh SM, Tow WK, Toh KM, Palanisamy UD, Sundralingam U. Exploring the Role of Herbal Compounds in Skin Aging: A Systematic Review of Topical Approaches. *Phytotherapy Research*. 2025 Jan;39(1):315-63.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.8375>
36. Gulen RB. Hypericum scabrum L.-infused locust bean gum/agar hydrogel film: A novel candidate for anti-aging facial mask applications. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. 2025 May 1;306:141673.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.141673>
37. Yahya EB, Ali SR, Lalung J, Zain MS, Danish M, John A. Exploring the potential of biopolymers in cosmetic applications: Sustainable, biocompatible, and high-performance materials for future innovations. *Polymer Engineering & Science*. 2025 Jun;65(6):2789-802.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/pen.27186>
38. Rode K, Rajankar N, Aalhate M, Mahajan S, Maji I, Gupta U, Singh PK. Hydrogels as Delivery Systems in Herbal Medicine. *Formulating Pharma-, Nutra-, and Cosmeceutical Products from Herbal Substances: Dosage Forms and Delivery Systems*. 2025 Aug 26:323-53.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119769484.ch12>
39. Kumar P, Verma A, Ashique S, Bhowmick M, Mohanto S, Singh A, Gupta M, Gupta A, Haider T. Unlocking the role of herbal cosmeceutical in anti-ageing and skin ageing associated diseases. *Cutaneous and Ocular Toxicology*. 2024 Jul 2;43(3):211-26.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15569527.2024.2380326>
40. Guo F, Danielski R, Santhiravel S, Shahidi F. Unlocking the nutraceutical potential of legumes and their by-products: Paving the way for the circular economy in the agri-food industry. *Antioxidants*. 2024 May 24;13(6):636.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox13060636>